

Agenda for Future Research

In the fields of:

- **Local communities and disasters**
- **Local environmental stewardship - Sustainability, transformation and behavioural change**

The ACCTING project explores the impact of Green Deal policies on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate and mitigate potential negative effects.

Its Agenda for Future Research highlights key research gaps across Green Deal policy areas and provides a clear overview of research priorities and needs for a fair and sustainable transition. By doing so, it aims to contribute to the development of future research agendas and pave the way for inclusive and effective policymaking and implementation.

The full set of research agendas covering other thematic areas can be found [on the ACCTING project website](#).

Theme: Local Communities and Disasters

ACCTING Findings

- Local communities hold valuable insights for mitigating, adapting and responding to climate-change-related disasters. However, their knowledge is often undervalued or insufficiently integrated into formal disaster management systems.
- Institutional change is needed to make the most of local social networks, material practices and knowledge systems.
- Gender and intersectional vulnerabilities remain insufficiently explored in disaster management. Gender+ considerations are crucial, as disasters disproportionately impact women, the elderly, disabled individuals, and marginalised groups.
- Women play critical but undervalued roles in community-level disaster prevention, preparedness and response, e.g., performing unseen and unrecognised work to strengthen and maintain social and material infrastructures.
- Women in leadership roles were crucial to some of the most successful examples of community organising.
- While authorities may recognise the value of local knowledge and inclusiveness, many fail to integrate it into their disaster management policies due to structural and institutional hinders, such as a lack of economic resources, bureaucratic rigidity and a top-down, paternalistic approach.
- Local knowledge is sometimes dismissed as unscientific or impractical, highlighting a disconnect between universal best practice and the context of policy implementation.
- Community organising has successfully filled gaps in disaster preparedness and response, especially in rural and under-resourced areas, e.g., community-led fire responses in Turkey and Sweden, and citizen-led flood monitoring committees in Italy.
- Vulnerabilities are exacerbated by systemic inequalities, such as socio-economic disadvantages, gender norms, and the exclusion of marginalised groups (like migrants) from decision-making.
- Migrant and minority communities often face heightened disaster risks due to housing in unsafe areas and limited access to information and resources.
- Many of the most successful and inclusive engagements between authorities and local communities involved hybrid authorities (e.g. multi-stakeholder expert groups), and mid-level mediators (e.g., community sentinels and spokespersons).

- Resilience was most evident when robust social and material infrastructures enabled a variety of interacting state and voluntary organisations to anticipate and respond to disaster in different ways.

Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Empowering Local Knowledge

Local communities possess valuable, context-specific knowledge regarding disaster prevention, preparedness and response. However, this knowledge is often overlooked or inadequately integrated into formal disaster management systems. Bridging this gap is essential to strengthen community resilience.

Research questions

- How can local knowledge be effectively incorporated into disaster risk reduction (DRR) policies and frameworks?
- What epistemic practices and institutional mechanisms are needed to bridge the gap between expert-driven approaches and community insights?

Subtheme 2. Gender+ Intersectionality

Disasters disproportionately affect women, the elderly, and other marginalised groups. Understanding how gender and intersectional vulnerabilities affect the possibility for mitigation and adaptation is key to more inclusive disaster management strategies.

Research questions

- How do intersecting social vulnerabilities influence disaster risk and response capabilities?
- What policies and practices can ensure the meaningful inclusion of marginalised groups in disaster preparedness?

Subtheme 3. Institutional Adaptation

Despite the recognition of local knowledge, inflexible bureaucratic systems may resist bottom-up, community-led approaches to disaster risk reduction (DRR). Institutional adaptation is necessary for fostering more inclusive and participatory disaster management strategies.

Research questions

- What cultural and structural changes are required to facilitate institutional adaptation in DRR?
- How can participatory models be scaled to enhance inclusiveness in disaster management?

Subtheme 4. Community-Driven Initiatives

Grassroots and community-driven initiatives play a crucial role in disaster management, particularly in under-resourced areas. However, these initiatives often lack long-term support and recognition from formal authorities, hindering their sustainability.

Research questions

- What funding and support programmes can sustain community-driven disaster preparedness efforts?
- How can authorities create the regulatory conditions that encourage and not foreclose community organising for DRR?

Subtheme 5. Addressing Systemic Inequalities

Disaster vulnerability is often compounded by socio-economic inequalities, with marginalised groups facing greater risks due to limited access to resources and decision-making power. Addressing these systemic inequalities is essential for effective disaster resilience.

Research questions

- What role can DRR policies and practices play in addressing intersecting social inequalities?
- How can policies for the broad social transformation that is needed to address social vulnerabilities and prevent disaster be properly integrated into existing state and regulatory responsibilities?

Subtheme 6. Behavioural and Social Change

Behavioural change in the context of disaster preparedness and response can occur both individually and collectively. A deeper exploration of the dynamics between individual action, and community and social transformation is needed to identify effective strategies.

Research questions

- How can individual and collective behavioural change complement each other in enhancing disaster prevention, preparedness and response?
- What are the most effective ways to engage individuals and communities in long-term disaster mitigation and adaptation strategies?

Subtheme 7. Youth Engagement and Intergenerational Knowledge

Young people, as well as the generational divide, have a crucial role in shaping future disaster resilience. Understanding their perspectives, as well as how to engage them in disaster preparedness, is vital.

Research questions

- How can youth be more effectively involved in community-based disaster management strategies?
- What role does intergenerational learning play in building resilience in vulnerable communities?

Subtheme 8. Polarisation in Disaster Management

Political polarisation and state dysfunction hinder community collaboration and effective risk reduction. Research into strategies for overcoming political partisanship and conflict in the context of climate-change-related disaster in Europe is needed.

Research questions

- What are the most effective strategies for overcoming polarisation in disaster management and collaborating across different groups?
- How do political conflict and consensus shape community participation in DRR?

Theme: Local environmental stewardship – Sustainability, transformation and behavioural change

ACCTING Findings

- The emergence of pro-nature behavioural change, particularly in vulnerable communities, is closely tied to cultural capital, role models, all inspiring and enabling the appearance of strong group activities. Traditional practices and intergenerational knowledge are important ingredients for pro-environment behavioural change and an inclusive discourse. Triggers for engagement and change are strongly linked to the neighbourhood e.g. the village.
- Effective knowledge sharing in movements focusing on environmental stewardship ignites participation and enables deeper individual or group transformation. However, gaps exist in the accessibility and practical application of special knowledge within communities. Identifying and re-visiting earlier experiences and knowledge but activating peer-networks contribute to enhance maturity of initiatives.
- Vulnerable groups face challenges in participation due to systemic barriers like socio-economic inequalities, lack of institutional support, and knowledge gaps. Our 11 cases show multiple vulnerabilities occurring from ethnic groups and status, lived tradition, gendered perspectives and especially rurality. Empowering these groups requires inclusive approaches, empathy and sensitive engagement patterns including e.g. a place based, neighbourhood solidarity discourse.
- Inclusive approaches with respecting differences, the special role of women, local non-privileged groups create durable activist movements. Female leadership re-percuss the neighbourhood presence and integrate an active gendered voice, often different from the market or job-income logic. Hence, unique barriers for participants occur across multiple and overlapping vulnerabilities and empowerment by external moderators can bridge existing gaps.
- Results of societal transformation beyond local neighbourhood concerns occur with previous empowering experience. The appearance of a true discourse about a possible inclusive future leaving no one behind creates shared resilience patterns. Project based action and urgent activist action create a productive discourse, capacities to initiate a durable change and to capitalize upon this discourse request special efforts – often beyond the intentions of focused movements. Anchoring new activities, capitalising on this resource is an inseparable ingredient of durable pro-environment behaviour.

Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Traditions and Intergenerational Exchange for Sustainability

Understanding how traditional practice and contemporary environmental action can positively interrelate is vital for the advancement of sustainable behaviours, particularly in vulnerable communities. Research on intergenerational knowledge dynamics can further inform pro-environment patterns for behavioural change.

Research questions

- How does traditional practice integrate with contemporary pro-environmental action and changing demands?
- What role do cultural and intergenerational narratives play in fostering pro-nature behaviours in vulnerable communities?

Subtheme 2. Knowledge Sharing and Transformation

Knowledge sharing is an important component of building up durable pro-environmental stewardship and collective action. However, there are gaps in accessibility and the practical application of environmental knowledge, particularly within communities facing socio-economic challenges.

Research questions

- How can peer exchange or digital marketplaces enhance environmental knowledge-sharing among communities?
- What are determining barriers for functioning knowledge transfer processes in pro-nature initiatives?

Subtheme 3. Gender and Intersectionality in Environmental Initiatives

Gender-specific factors and intersectional vulnerabilities influence the appearance and build-up; the ability to participate in environmental initiatives; and finally, the wider impact of initiatives.

Understanding the gender dynamics of the build-up phase and durable action can lead to more equitable and inclusive pro-environment activities.

Research questions

- How do intersectional vulnerabilities influence engagement in pro-nature initiatives in leading positions and what specific challenges do women face in leadership roles in environmental movements?
- How can successful leadership patterns and role models appear that link to durable action?

Subtheme 4. Participation Challenges and Inclusivity

Systemic barriers hinder marginalised groups, rural people or traditional culture practicing groups from participation in environmental initiatives. To increase inclusivity, robust evidence frameworks are needed that capture diverse voices e.g. in support programmes. Over time this can guide steps to empower vulnerable groups to take part in sustainability efforts.

Research questions

- How can inclusive frameworks of pro-nature engagement be developed that address participation barriers?
- What role can institutional and project-based support play in empowering marginalised groups and what are fitting indicators for inclusive participation?

Subtheme 5. Tension between Economic and Environmental Impacts on neighbourhoods

Tensions between economic prosperity and environmental sustainability are a significant challenge, especially in vulnerable communities and when affecting living places, neighbourhoods. Exploring how those tensions are perceived in the community but also how such situations are contextualised, operationalised by powerful business players can inspire new insights. Understanding powerful players and their influence on neighbourhoods under pressure is an important determinant to understand barriers for a more inclusive participation in pro-environment action.

Research questions

- How do dedicated resistive communities address the tension between environmental sustainability and the interests of economic players, especially in economically disadvantaged areas?
- What is the evidence for successful strategies of administrations to balance successfully economic pressures with sustainability goals in areas with presence of vulnerable groups?

Subtheme 6. Re-building Environmental Stewardship

Traditional use practice and new practice of civil society engagement for the environment have important roles for building up environmental stewardship, particularly for marginalised and vulnerable groups. Research can contribute to assess the impact of current pro-environment action and identify effective ways to move from short term urgent civic action to durable long-term models of engagement leading to sustained behavioural change.

Research questions

- What are proven pathways to best embed durable environmental engagement in vulnerable communities and what are critical success factors, benchmarks for durable initiatives?
- How do conceptually recently applied approaches as the natural commons, the multispecies dimension or participatory governance integrate effectively with pro-nature action involving vulnerable groups?

About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

As the project approaches its conclusion in May 2025, the research team has developed a Research Agenda outlining key knowledge gaps across Green Deal policy areas. This document serves as a valuable reference for future research and policymaking.

Discover the [Research Agenda published during the first research cycle](#).

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